

On the Szeged Index of monocyclic graphs

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Szeged index (S_z) is a new topological index based on distances between vertices of a graph. It is the extension of Wiener index (W) on cyclic graphs. These indices of cyclic molecules differ, in the general case, S_z exceeds W . Otherwise, the relation between S_z and W of cyclic molecules is not yet established thoroughly. In order to get some information about this relations, we have examined monocyclic molecules consisting n vertices ($n = \text{even}, > \text{ or } = 4$) and observed that $S_z = 2W$.

Distance properties of molecular graphs form an important topic in chemical graph theory. These properties appear to be a convenient source for deriving molecular descriptors¹⁻⁴. There are a number of distance indices available in the literature⁵. The current interest in distance indices is stimulated by their use in non-empirical⁶ quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR) and quantitative structure-activity relationships⁷ (QSAR). To justify this statement we recall the famous Wiener index (W) which is also known as the Wiener number⁸ (W). The topological index W , conceived by Wiener almost half a century ago, is one of the most thoroughly studied, best understood and most frequently used molecular-shape descriptors in chemical graph theory. It found numerous applications in the modeling of a variety of physicochemical, pharmaceutical and biological properties of organic molecules, and its theory is equally well developed^{3,4}.

Another generalization of the Wiener index W , for cyclic graphs has recently been put forward by Gutman and coworkers^{9,10}. Gutman⁹ introduced a novel topological index which eventually was named¹⁰ the Szeged index and denoted by S_z . For acyclic molecules the S_z is, by definition, equal to W . For cyclic molecules S_z and W differ and not much is known on their relationships¹¹. Infact, S_z is considered as the modification of W for cycles. It is thus more important than W in cyclic molecules.

Mathematical properties and chemical applications of S_z have been described in recent works¹²⁻⁴². It has been established that $S_z(G) > W(G)$ for all connected graphs and $S_z(G) = W(G)$ if and only if all blocks of G are complete. Note that every block of G is a true vertex complete graph^{9,13}. Thus, the indices S_z and W of cyclic molecules differ and not much is known on their relationships. Excep-

tionally, the cyclic graphs for which $S_z = W$ were fully characterized^{12,13} and it has been shown²⁰ that for all connected graphs $S_z > W$. In addition to this several anomalies were established in the behaviour of S_z of benzonide system^{10,14,18} and some other related polycyclic bipartite graphs¹⁶.

In order to get additional information on the relation between S_z and W in cyclic molecules, we have decided to investigate monocyclic graphs containing even number of vertices ($n > 4$). It may be recalled that n -vertex unicyclic graphs possess n -edges. Also, that the edge set of monocyclic graph ($n = \text{even}; n > 4$) can be partitioned into $n/2(n > 4)$ classes of parallel edges. It may be noted that the number of edges in an elementary cuts of such monocyclic graphs will always be 2.

Notation and terminology used to define S_z and W : Let G be the usual, hydrogen atom depleted, graph representation of the molecule under consideration^{10,11}. Hence, G is a connected graph without directed and multiple edges and without loops. By $V(G)$ and $E(G)$ we denote the vertex and edge sets, respectively, of G . If e is an edge of G , connecting the vertices u and v , then we write, $e = uv$. The number of vertices of G is denoted by $|G|$.

The distance between the vertices of G is defined as usual¹² : the distance $d(u,v|G)$, between two vertices u and v of G is equal to the length of shortest path connecting these vertices.

Definition of Wiener index (W)^{3,8} : The Wiener index (W) of a graph G is just the sum of distances of all pairs of vertices of G ,

$$W = W(G) = 1/2 \sum_{v \in V(G)} \sum_{u \in V(G)} \delta(u, u|G) \quad (1)$$

$$= 1/2 \sum_{v \in V(G)} d(v|G)$$

where, $d(v|G)$ is called the distance number of vertex v and is defined¹⁰ as

$$d(v|G) = \sum_{u \in V(G)} d(v, u|G)$$

Definition of Szeged index (S_2)^{9,10} : Let $e = uv \in E(G)$. Then we define two subsets of vertex set of G as

$$N_1(e|G) = \{x \in V(G) | d(x, u|G) < d(x, v|G)\}$$

$$N_2(e|G) = \{x \in V(G) | d(x, u|G) > d(x, v|G)\}$$

The number of elements of $N_1(e|G)$ and $N_2(e|G)$ are denoted by $n_1(e|G)$ and $n_2(e|G)$, respectively. Thus, $n_1(e|G)$ counts the vertices of G lying closer to the vertex u than to vertex v . The meaning of $n_2(e|G)$ is analogous. The vertices equidistant from both ends of the edge uv belong neither to $N_1(e|G)$ nor to $N_2(e|G)$.

The Szeged index of the graph G is defined as

$$S_2(G) = S_2 = \sum_{e \in E(G)} n_1(e|G)n_2(e|G) \quad (2)$$

Wiener index (W) of monocyclic graphs ($n = \text{even}, n > 4$) in linear time²⁶ : Let G be a monocyclic graph consisting of n -vertices ($n = \text{even}, > 4$) and let E_1 and E_2 denote the edges of G of a given direction. For $i = 1, 2$, let G_i be the graph which is obtained by deleting all the edges of E_i . It may be noted that the connected components of graph G_i are paths. A graph T_i whose vertices are connected components of G_i , then every T_i is a tree and moreover the mapping

$$\alpha : V(G) \rightarrow V(T_1 \times T_2 \times T_3 \times \dots \times T_{n/2}) \quad (3)$$

defined as $\alpha(v) = (v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_{n/2})$, is an isometric embedding. Here v_i is the vertex set of T_i corresponding to the connected component of G_i containing v . We call the mapping α the canonical embedding of the monocyclic graph considered. Also that for the graphs under present study v_i is always equal to $n/2$. It may be recalled that T_i is also $n/2$.

We now invoke a concept of the Wiener index (W) on weighted graph¹⁴. A vertex-weighted graph (G, w) is a graph G together with a function $w : V(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^+$. The Wiener number, $W(G, w)$ of a weighted graph (G, w) is defined as

$$W(G, w) = 1/2 \sum_{u, v \in V(G)} w(u)w(v)d(u, v). \quad (4)$$

For the monocyclic graphs under present study, let $T_1, T_2, T_3, \dots, T_{n/2}$ be the trees from canonical embedding. For $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n/2$, we introduce weighted trees (T_i, w_i) as

follows : for $u \in T_i$ let $w_i(u)$ be the number of vertices of x of G such that the i -th component of $\alpha(x)$ is u . In other words, $w_i(u)$ is just a number of vertices in the connected components of G_i , which corresponds to vertex u . Thus, we can write²⁶,

$$W(G) = \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} W(T_i, w_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} n^2/4 = n^3/8 \quad (5)$$

It may be recalled that for the graphs under consideration, the components of G_i will always be a path consisting of $n/2$ vertices and that the number of such paths for G_i will always be $n/2$. Finally, the total number of G_i will be $n/2$. We illustrate this by the following example.

Let G be a monocyclic graph containing eight vertices (Fig. 1). Then the connected components $G_i = n/2 = 8/2 = 4 (G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4)$. These graphs G_1, G_2, G_3 and G_4 are ob-

Fig. 1. Monocyclic graph containing eight vertices.

tained from G by deleting all edges ($n/2$) of a given direction respectively as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

It may be observed that the connected components of the graphs G_i are paths. The weight of a given vertex in the weighted tree (T_i, w_i) is simply the number of vertices in the corresponding components of G_i , which in the present case is $n/2 = 4$. Thus, we have

$$W(T_1, w_1) = W(T_2, w_2) = W(T_3, w_3) = W(T_4, w_4) \quad (6)$$

$$= 4 \times 4 = 16$$

Therefore,

$$W(G) = 16 + 16 + 16 + 16 = 64.$$

Szeged index (S_2) of monocyclic graph ($n = \text{even}, n > 4$) : Let G be the monocyclic graph ($n = \text{even}, n > 4$). It may be recalled that a straight-line segment C with end points p and q is called a cut segment. If C is orthogonal to one of the $n/2$ edge direction, each p and q is the centre of the edge, and the graph obtained from G removing all edges intercepted by C has exactly two connected components. The cut is the set of edges intercepted by a cut segment.

For an edge e of T_1 for the monocyclic graph under present study, let $f(e)$ be the number of edges in the cut of G separating the path corresponding to its end-vertices. It may be recalled that for the graph considered $f(e)$ will always be equal to 2. Then, we can write,

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1 &= S_1(G) = \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \sum_{e \in T_1} f(e) n_1(e) n_2(e) \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \sum_{e \in T_1} 2n_1(e) n_2(e) \\
 &= \sum_{i=1}^{n/2} \sum_{e \in T_1} n^2/2 = n^3/4 \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

The graph mentioned above with eight vertices may be considered again. Then as for the Wiener index, we construct the weighted trees (T_i, w_i) . In addition, for all edges e of these trees, we compute $f(e)$, i.e. the number of edges in the cut components of e , which in the graphs considered is always two. Then, the Szeged index (S_2) of the referred monocyclic graph ($n = 8$) will be given by the expression,

$$S_2 = S_2(G) = 2(4 \times 4)4 = 128 \tag{8}$$

Hence, for a monocyclic graph ($n = 12$), we can have Fig. 3. Then the connected components $G_i = n/2 = 12/2 =$

Fig. 3

$6(G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5, G_6)$. These graphs G_1, G_2, G_3, G_4, G_5 and G_6 are obtained from G by deleting all edges ($n/2$) of a given direction respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4

Therefore, W can be computed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 W(T_1, w_2) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 W(T_2, w_2) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 W(T_3, w_3) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 W(T_4, w_4) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 W(T_5, w_5) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 W(T_6, w_6) &= 6 \times 6 = 36 \\
 \hline
 W &= 216
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Wiener index $W = (6 \times 6)6 = 216$

Therefore, S_2 can be computed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_2(T_1, w_1) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 S_2(T_2, w_2) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 S_2(T_3, w_3) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 S_2(T_4, w_4) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 S_2(T_5, w_5) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 S_2(T_6, w_6) &= 2(6 \times 6) = 72 \\
 \hline
 S_2 &= 432
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, Szeged index $S_2 = 2(6 \times 6)6 = 432$

The W and S_2 indices for the monocyclic graphs corresponding to size (n) ranging from 4 to 10. $n =$ even, are computed as discussed above and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Computed Wiener (W) and Szeged (S_2) indices for some monocyclic graphs ($n =$ even, $n > 4$)

Sl no	n	W	S_2	S_2/W
1	4	8	16	2
2.	6	27	54	2
3.	8	64	128	2
4	10	125	250	2
5.	12	216	432	2
6.	14	343	686	2
7.	16	512	1024	2
8.	18	729	1458	2
9	20	1000	2000	2

The perusal of Table 1 indicates that in all the cases S_2 index is found to be twice than the corresponding W index of the respective monocyclic graphs. We can thus conclude that for monocyclic graphs ($n =$ even, $n > 4$) the Szeged index will always be double than the corresponding Wiener index, i.e.

$$S_2(G)_{n=\text{even}, >4} = 2W(G)_{n=\text{even}, >4} \tag{9}$$

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